

#31

Evaluation & Impact Assessment
**STAKEHOLDER-ASSOCIATED
RISK ANALYSIS**

MAA Scenario

When to Implement

Useful during all stages of the initiative, although mostly in the planning stage and iteratively throughout the project.

Group Size

Any size. If the initiative has a big network, the tools would be more useful.

Level of Technical Difficulty

Chart interpretation and basic knowledge on project management.

Time Needed

40 minutes approx.

Resources Required

Access to a computer, tablet or phone that has the MS Office package installed.

Clustering with Other Tools

Tools # 1, 3.

PURPOSE, BACKGROUND & LOGIC

Image source: [Roman Synkevych on Unsplash](#)

Purpose

The tool is useful to guide the reflections of innovators toward an analysis of potential risks associated with specific actors and the context where the initiative is inserted.

Background and Logic

The identification and management of risks is a crucial element in project management, mainly because they allow us to maintain control, and anticipate those situations that may compromise the desired objectives. Although risks are present in different ways and in relative amounts depending on the scale of the initiative and the resources involved.

Dashboards are commonly used for self-evaluation in project management because it is considered the most efficient way to monitor performance through multiple data sources.

In general, regardless of the area in which the initiative activities occur, it is always exposed to a certain risk that can negatively or positively impact the development of the initiative. For this reason, it is necessary to study and evaluate the risks that the initiative may face to the point of being able to counteract them. Risk prevention allows, among many other benefits, to reduce costs, meet technical specifications, or perform activities according to the initiative schedule.

When deciding to innovate interactively, one of the fundamental elements is the participation of actors. Each of them has certain points of view and can take unforeseen actions throughout the development of the initiative generating problems. To counteract these possible risks, it is important to have risk identification and management processes, focusing in part on analysing the diverse opinions and ideas of all those involved in the initiative to identify the risks to which they could be related. Knowing and preventing risks as much as possible increases the capacity to respond to the various inconveniences that may arise, which can provide optimization of cost, time, and quality of results.

This tool can be used in conjunction with Tool #1 and 5, as good instruments to start planning initial actions.

Materials

- MS Excel file.

METHOD/HOW-TO GUIDE

This tool uses data visualization techniques that guide the user's reflection, showing the data in an easy and accessible way. Allows for simple analysis of results, facilitating interpretation and decision making.

What Do You Need? How to Prepare For it?

To use this tool, it is necessary to have access to a computer, tablet, or phone that has the Office package installed. The Excel file is both the analysis matrix and the template to collect information. The first tab is used to enter the information, while the next is created automatically, allowing the data to be viewed. If the data collection process wants to be done outside the Excel program, it is sufficient to print the first tabs of the Excel. However, to use the visualization system, data entry is required.

Excel Structure

This tool is made up of two tabs, named: *data entry* and *graphical results*. The first tab is composed of a matrix divided into five columns that allow each of the actors to be related to the risks or problems of the initiative, assigning a value for the frequency and impact, according to the preestablished levels. On the other hand, the second tab shows the graphical results of the analysis of risks associated with the actors.

Data Entry

When opening the Excel file, the user must enter the information into the "Data entry" tab. Once placed in this tab, the user will find five columns, namely: *risks*, *actor*, *frequency*, *impact*, and *risk level*.

The first column 'Risks' is subdivided into five different risk typologies. There, the risks are already predefined by the tool because it has been tried to facilitate the reflection process, including the most common risks that affect interactive innovation initiatives. Although, in the subdivision of "Other risks" at the end of the table, there are blank spaces that can be filled in freely by the user if considered pertinent. If more space is needed, the option 'Insert row' can be used up to the number of 60 rows.

In the second column 'Actor', the names of the actors related to the risks detailed in the first column must be included. The user should reflect on which actor involved or not in the initiative is most related to this specific inconvenience that may be happening. It can be an institution name or a generic descriptor for a group of actors. If a risk is present in the initiative, but it has no relation to any actor in concrete, it can be marked as "General" and will be visualised in this way.

Then, in columns three and four 'Frequency', 'Impact', the values referring to frequency and impact associated with risks must be included, that is, a number from 0 to 5 that must correspond to the criteria explained in the upper section of the Data Entry tab, in a table called '*Description of criteria for frequency and impact assessment*'.

Finally, column five 'Risk level', which will show the intensity of the risk, that is, the result of a calculation automatically generated by the tool from the values that refer to the frequency and impact of the risks previously provided by the user. The value obtained will change the format of the cell, and a primary interpretation of the results can be made through the legend displayed in the upper section of the table. This column has not to be modified, although the automatic calculation, as well as the associated conditional formatting, does not work correctly.

The input information necessary for the use of this tool can be obtained in several ways:

- The initiative manager autonomously;
- Through a meeting with the initiative's steering committee;
- Through a participatory workshop with the members of the team and the closest parties;

The above tools can be integrated to average the results. However, it should be noted that the more participatory the information gathering, the more objective the result will be.

LIAISON Tool #31: Stakeholder-Associated Risk Analysis

Data entry			
DESCRIPTION OF THE CRITERIA FOR THE ASSESSMENT OF FREQUENCY AND IMPACT			
Frequency		Impact	
How often was it or can it be presented?		What was or could be the impact of each factor?	
It can not happen		No consequences	
Unlikely		Mild consequences	
Moderately likely		Moderate consequences	
Probable		Relevant consequences	
Highly probable		Serious consequences	
It will surely pass		Project abandonment	

Related Actors	Frequency	Impact	Risk's level
			Do not modify this column
Actor 3	0	0	0
Actor 4	2	4	8
Actor 5	1	1	1
Actor 6	3	1	3
Actor 6	4	2	8

Risk's Level	
0	No risk
1 - 6	Low risk
7 - 16	Risky
17 - 25	Very risky

Data entry | Graphical results

Illustration 1. Screenshot of the "Data entry" tab.

EXPECTED RESULTS

Once the values have been inserted into the "Data entry" tab, the user must go to the other tab to see the results obtained.

If the results are not displayed automatically, it will be necessary to refresh the data (Select Data > Refresh All)

Graphical Results

In this tab, there is a bar graph that represents the risk values associated with the actors, and each bar has the intensity of each risk detailed on the upper side. This graph groups together the risks that have been associated with a given actor, allowing one to identify the most critical actors, who would possibly require more attention during the development of the initiative. On the other hand, through this graph, it is easy to see which risks have the greatest potential to generate problems throughout the activities, being those with the highest bars and considered very risky. The highest value is 30, which would imply that it is a very frequent risk and that it would also cause serious damage to the initiative. Risks that have been marked in the data entry tab, but that result in a value of 0 are not displayed in this graph. In this visualization, the results are interpreted according to a legend described in the table on the right side of the tab.

Illustration 2. Screenshot of the tab 'Graphical results'.

